

IN-LINE QUALITY CONTROL SYSTEM FOR THE INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION OF MULTIAXIAL NON-CRIMP FABRICS

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ABSTRACT

A new approach is presented in which existing systems for error detection are used to build up a closed loop control for quality optimization in the production process of NCF. Only with this online system, productivity and product quality can be increased. The fibre material is screened for fibre disorientation and gaps and deviations in areal weight at different positions alongside the production line using state of the art equipment for error detection. Additionally, the machine-parameters are monitored and the yarn tension of both reinforcement fibres and stitching yarn are measured continuously. An automated and self-learning control is developed that automatically adjusts the settings of the production machine. By this, a minimum of errors in the textile is achieved. In addition, the quantitative description generated in the process is used to develop an error map for each batch of material produced. This error map allows for production waste to be minimized, as the produced material can be automatically sorted into different quality grades, meeting the demands of different customers. Furthermore, the material cutting can be adjusted that only low quality areas are removed. By this, only high quality material will be used for the component part production. An entire roll of non-crimp fabric would not be declared as waste. The quality control is realized by an automatic control device. By a pressure roll in front of the warp knitting unit the rovings are homogenized.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of fibre reinforced composites is getting a new standard in lightweight constructions. Due to their great mechanical properties and low density of the materials in comparison to metal materials, composites find their way into more and more application fields. In the automotive and aerospace industry as well as for wind power plants, both glass and carbon fibre reinforced composites are the state of the art solution regarding weight reduction and performance improvement [6]. Textiles used for the composite production exist in various forms of textile architecture. This can be for instance: nonwoven, braids, woven fabric or non-crimp fabrics (NCF). Commonly, multiaxial non-crimp fabrics are used as semi-finished fabrics for fibre reinforcement plastics. In NCF reinforced composites, the fibres are not crimped and have therefore substantial in-plane orientation. This fact results in high mechanical properties of the textile in various directions depending on the numbers of layers and the angle of the fibre lay-up. NCF production takes place on a warp knitting machine with multi-axial weft insertion. [8] For the production of multiaxial NCFs the straight reinforcement fibres (rovings or spread tows) are laid parallel in a defined angle. Several layers are laid on top of each other. Directly after the fibre placement all layers are joined with a warp knitted technology with a standard Polyester

yarn. By this, the so-produced fabric can be wound up and handled during the upcoming preform steps. In Figure 1, a non-crimp fabric is illustrated.

Figure 1: Non-Crimp Fabric [7]

Due to the increasing amount of application of fibre reinforced composites, the quality of the produced fabrics takes on more and more prominence these days. The industry requires to process only high quality material to acquire the highest possible mechanical properties of the composite part. Low quality material is declared as waste or is only used for low performance application. The quality impairment occurs directly during the NCF production. Due to a non-uniform fibre tension, gaps or thick spots appear between single fibre rovings. As this error happens irregularly, various areas of the NCF have very poor quality and are not used as reinforcement. Since the industry needs to know which areas of the produced fabric are of high quality, the usage of quality control systems is inevitable [9].

To investigate the properties of produced fabrics, various solutions exist for monitoring the quality of multiaxial non-crimp, braided and woven fabrics as well as preforms. Those technologies are limited to the singular inspection of their area of application, such as breakage of weft or knitting yarns [1, 12], discontinuous measurements [5], off-line measurement [4, 5, 10] and qualitative instead of quantitative acquisition of defects [2, 11, 12] as well as focus on the inspected materials (e.g. only carbon fibres) [13, 14]. Special sensors for the acquisition of the area density were developed for this purpose [15]. But so far combinations of the stand-alone solutions to acquire and document all defects as a whole are non-existent. In addition to that the gained data is not used for quality management of the running process.

Existing measuring procedures to acquire defects in interplies are limited to carbon fibre fabrics and show low resolutions [13, 14] or are only used off-line [4, 5, 10]. Image analyzing systems are currently solely able to inspect the top layers. Defects like gaps are mainly caused by the knitting process and therefore only occur in the interplies afterwards. Bi-axial non-crimp fabrics are therefore attractive for mass production as no interplies have to be investigated [3].

All these monitoring systems allow a detection of the fabrics offline and are stand-alone solutions. Nowadays, no inline-system exists that allows a continuous and permanent quality monitoring including thorough quality documentation [9]. A quantitative acquisition and documentation of defects (gaps between reinforcement fibres, thick spots, angle deviation of the reinforcement fibres and voids) of multiaxial non-crimp fabrics is the key for a high productivity. An overall system that gathers material- and process parameters as well as defects has still to be developed.

This overall system development is performed in the AiF Auto-NCF project funded by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi), Germany, with three project partners: ITA and WZL of RWTH Aachen University and the IfU as Assoc. Institute of RWTH Aachen University, Germany.

In this project an in-line quality control system is developed. By the use of different sensors, the process parameters are tracked during the manufacturing process. Areal weight is detected by an X-ray sensor while fibre misalignments, gaps and thick spots are detected with a camera system (see chapter 2). In Figure 2 the overall concept of the in-line quality control system is shown. The goal is a real-time control system. With this system it becomes possible to record material and process parameters as well as defects. The result is an error map in which all defects are recorded with type, location and category. Each produced fabric roll is delivered to the customer in the downstream process including its unique error map. By the use of this error map, all areas of each produced textile are defined and the industry can process the best suited areas. As industrial companies have different requirements regarding the textile quality, the amount of waste material and the quality costs can be reduced tremendously.

Figure 2: In-line quality control system on a warp knitting machine with multi-axial weft insertion

2 MACHINE MODIFICATIONS

In this chapter, the realized machine modifications are described. In Figure 3 the integration of different components in the LIBA COPCENTRA MAX 3 CNC, Liba, Naila, Germany, machine at the ITA, Aachen, Germany is shown. The components are installed at the machine by the company Protechna Herbst GmbH & Co. KG, Ottobrunn, Germany. The fibre material is screened for fiber disorientation and gaps at different positions alongside the production line. Additionally, the machine parameters are monitored and the yarn tension of both reinforcement fibres and warp knitting yarns are measured continuously. Furthermore, a yarn breakage detection system is installed.

The yarn breakage detection is realized by an air blow unit. This unit is installed next to the warp knitting yarns. Fibre breakage is detected with a visible red light laser with 660 nm. As soon as a fibre breaks, that fibre is blown into the light-barrier which stops the machine.

Furthermore, a camera system is installed to realize the fibre screening regarding fibre misalignments and gaps. This system includes a DSP-Box and two cameras (one in front and one in the back of the warp knitting unit).

Moreover, a pressure roll is integrated right in front of the warp knitting unit of the machine. In Figure 4 this set-up is illustrated. By the use of this pressure roll it becomes possible to homogenize the roving layers. The pressure applied on the roll is adjusted with springs on each side. The set pressure influences the formation of gaps. A uniform pressure across the width of the fabric realizes the reduction of gaps and fibre misalignments.

Furthermore, a real-time machine vision system for areal weight detection and fibre orientation are to be installed in the next steps. By the integration of all these components the overall model based closed loop control regarding a self-configuration pressure roll will be realized.

Figure 3: Integration of the light-barrier, air blow unit and camera system in the machine

The images taken by the camera system are compared before and after the warp knitting process step. If the cameras detect a defect, the pressure roll pressure is adjusted according to the recorded defect. Appropriate controlling strategies are developed and validated with a functional model so that a closed loop control is realized. Through this the desired target values, e.g. gap frequency, are obtained automatically and adjusted by the pressure roll.

At the same time the camera installed after the warp knitting unit is recording all defect information and saves them in the error map.

Figure 4: Integration of the pressure roll in the machine set-up

3 METHODS

To investigate the influence of the pressure roll on the propagation of gaps, various trials have been performed. Load cells to measure pre-load and operation loads have been installed at the machine (see figure 5). The implementation of a pressure measurement film is used to determine the load distribution. This pressure measurement film indicates applied pressure differences along the width of the measurement area. The film was placed below the pressure roll covering the entire width.

Furthermore, the homogenizing effect of the compression roll for different settings is investigated. Various machine speeds from 30 m/h (low speed) up to 150 m/h (high speed) are combined with

different spring loads varying from 50 to 100 N. In addition two different areal weights are investigated: 300 g/m² and 600 g/m² per layer. PPG Hybon glass fibres with 600 tex have been used for all trials.

Figure 5: Installation of load cells

4 RESULTS

The examinations with the pressure measurement film show a curved, irregular characteristic of the force along the pressure rolls. As shown in figure 6, the pressure indicating film is suitable for the localization of gaps and thick spots. Clearly the pressure peaks depict the thick spots and the troughs depict the gaps in the fabric. The edges of the gaps display higher peaks than anywhere else in the fabric because the missing rovings accumulate at the edges of the gaps and create thick spots which result in a high pressure on the pressure-measurement-sheet. Conclusions about the height and width of thick spots can be drawn from the resulting force distribution.

Figure 6: Forced gaps in a produced fabric

In figure 7, the results of the use of the pressure roll is shown. For 300 g/m² areal weight per layer and low production speed, the number of gaps can be reduced significantly if a pressure roll is used. For low areal weights a low tension shows the best results. For 600 g/m² areal weight per layer and low production speed, a high tension applied on the fabric shows good results regarding gap distribution and homogenization.

The best fabric appearance for a biaxial non-crimp fabric with an area weight of 300 g/m² per layer is achieved with a high roving tension, a low production speed and a spring force of 70 N to 80 N each spring. This equals a compression force of 171.7 N to 187.5 N. The trials with a low thread tension did not result in adequate fabric appearances.

Figure 7: Result of the use of a pressure roll

5 CONCLUSION

It can be pointed out that the pressure roll system increases significantly the homogenization of the fabric. By this, the next level of quality in the NCF production can be reached.

To compensate gaps different compression forces can be set in the machine control panel depending on roving tension, areal density and machine speed. Thus the integration of a self-configuration pressure roll system in combination with a camera system, which is independent from the machine control panel and adjusts the compression force automatically with a change in layer structure, textile- or process parameters as well with the occurrence of defects, is reasonable. A spring force setting between 70 N and 80 N shows the best results regarding fibre misalignments. Based on that value the force is adjusted at the detection of a gap. An automatic control enables a defined setting of the compression force. Through automatically controllable pressure rolls the same fabric with similar characteristic is producible after any period of time. Additionally the product quality is increased significantly through the reduction of thick spots and gaps. In the next steps the further optimization of the pressure roll would therefore result in an enhancement of the composite part characteristics.

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REFERENCES

- [1] BTSR International S.P.A., *SMART MATRIX WARP – Production control system*, Oligate Olona Italy, BTSR International S.P.A., Firmenschrift, 2010.
- [2] Elbit Vision System Ltd., *IQ-TEX 4 Trademark – Vision Empowered Process Monitoring*, <http://www.evs.co.il>, 05.06.2012.
- [3] C. Greb, A. Schnabel, J. Haring, T. Gries, Evaluation of novel preforming technologies for large-scale composite production, In: Beckwith, W. Scott, M. Maher, M. Newaz, G. Reyes-Villaneuav (Eds.): *Emerging Oppoertunities: Materials and Process Solutions, Sampe 2012 Conference & Exhibition*, May 21-24, 2012, Balimore, Maryland, 2012.
- [4] U. Hassler, S. Schloetzer, R. Hanke, Computed tomography for analysis of fiber distribution in carbon fiber preforms, *International Symposium on Digital Industrial Radiology and Computed Tomography (DIR)*, Lyon, France, 2007.
- [5] U. Hassler, M. Rehak, R. Hanke, Carbon Fibre Preform Inspection by Circular X-ray Tomosynthesis, *IEEE Nuclear Science Symposium*, Dresden, 2008.
- [6] R. Lässig, M. Eisenhut, A. Mathias, et. al., *Serienproduktion von hochfesten Faserverbundbauteilen. Perspektiven für den deutschen Maschinen- und Anlagenbau*, Studie, Roland Berger Strategy Consultants, September, 2012.
- [7] LIBA Maschinenfabrik GmbH, *Kettenwirkautomat mit multiaxialem Schußeintrag COPCENTRA MAX 3*, Booklet, Naila, 2003.
- [8] S. V. Lomov, *Non-Crimp Fabric Composites: Manufacturing, Properties and Applications*, CRC Press, 2011.
- [9] C. Mersmann, *Industrialisierende Maschine-Vision-Integration im Faserverbundleichtbau. Ergebnisse aus der Produktionstechnik*, Bd. 8/2012, Apprimus Verlag, Aachen, 2012.
- [10] S. Mohr, S. Gayetskyy, U. Haßler, R. Hanke, Konturangepasste Lagenextraktion aus Computertomographie-Daten von Faserverbundwerkstoffen. *DGZfP-Jahrestagung 2009. Zerstörungsfreie Materialprüfung, ZfP in Forschung, Entwicklung und Anwendung*, Münster, Germany, Mai 18-20, 2009.
- [11] Multiaxial und Biaxial, *Protechna ProCam System is watching you*, Kettenwirk-Praxis 1/2010, KARL MAYER Textilmaschinenfabrik GmbH, Obertshausen, 2010.
- [12] Protechna Herbst GmbH & Co. KG, Ottobrunn, <http://www.protechna.de>, 09.04.2015.
- [13] M. Schulze, H. Heuer, Zerstörungsfreie Prüfung von CFK-Gelegen mit Hochfrequenz-Wirbelstrom, *Fraunhofer-Allianz Leichtbau Tagung: Vom Konzept zum Produkt In Geschlossenen Ketten Denken!*, Darmstadt, Februar, 2011.
- [14] M. Schulze, M. Küttner, H. Heuer, N. Meyendorf, Mehrfrequenz-Wirbelstromprüfverfahren zur Qualitätskontrolle bei der Produktion von Kohlefaser-Multiaxialgelegen, *DGZfP-Jahrestagung 2009. Zerstörungsfreie Materialprüfung, ZfP in Forschung, Entwicklung und Anwendung*, Münster, Germany, Mai 18-20, 2009.
- [15] ZAP Systemkomponenten GmbH + Co. KG, *Echtzeitmessung: Flächengewicht, Warendicke, Dichte*, ZAP Systemkomponenten GmbH + Co. KG, Straubing, 2010.